

MODELLING VARIABILITY OF TOW ORIENTATION FOR WOVEN TEXTILE COMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

Thermoforming of textile composites is potentially a cost-effective manufacturing technique for mass production. To aid process optimization, accurate and reliable computer aided engineering tools are required. Finite Element (FE) simulation of the textile forming process provides such a tool and needs appropriate constitutive models for material behaviour, tool-ply and ply-ply friction [1-5]. In addition, an ability to predict typical variability of the tow direction within the forming sheet is desirable. Accurately characterizing and modeling a fabric's inherent tow directional variability is important when predicting its effect on the fabric's draping behaviour and on the textile composite's part final mechanical properties [6-8]. Previously Yu et al [9] aimed to do this by introducing a simple Monte Carlo approach for assigning fibre orientation and the shear angle to elements of the initial blank. However, assigning these parameters in a stochastic manner was found to cause discontinuity and disturbances in the yarn-paths, leading to spurious tensile loads during forming simulations. Skordos and Sutcliffe [7] developed a novel method of characterising and modelling the variability of tow direction in woven composite materials using two integrated approaches; the first was based on the use of Fourier transforms to determine the orientation of yarns, the second was a spatial linkage search; a

technique that produced good predictions of the unit-cell positions.

The aim of the current work is to: (a) characterize the variability of tow orientation in a range of engineering fabrics and (b) reproduce statistically representative variability in FE meshes that can subsequently be used in forming simulations without producing spurious tensile stresses.

2 Materials

Two different engineering fabrics and a textile composite have been analysed in this investigation:

- a plain weave glass fabric; weft tow width = 2.18 +/- 0.038 mm, warp tow width = 2.12 +/- 0.052mm; areal density = 311 g/m² (ECK12 Allscot)
- a plain weave self-reinforced polypropylene fabric; weft tow width = 2.55 +/- 0.1mm, warp tow width = 2.52 +/- 0.06mm; areal density = 123 g/m² (Armordon)
- a preconsolidated 2x2 twill weave, co-mingled glass / polypropylene composite; weft tow width = 5.06 +/- 0.45mm, warp tow width = 5.71 +/- 0.59mm; areal density = 760 g/m² (Twintex).

The glass fabric was analysed both after taking directly 'off the roll' and also after manual handling.

3 Image Processing

3.1 Manual Image Analysis Method

In order to determine the statistical distribution of tow angles, nine square samples measuring 300x300 mm were cut from each material. Hand-drawn grids following the tows of the two ‘off the roll’ textiles, the preconsolidated sheet and the manually handled glass fabric were drawn to determine the nodal coordinates of the corners of each grid-cell, the coordinates of which were determined from images using the image analysis code, ‘ImageJ’ [10] (see Figure 1).

Fig.1. (a) Image of variability in an actual textile, (b) Image of the mesh produced from the Matlab code

Subsequently, nodal and element matrices were manually written inside a spreadsheet and subsequently fed to a Matlab code which produced a mesh consisting of quadrilateral elements. The angle at the bottom corner of each cell was automatically determined by the code (see Figure 1b). The distribution of the angles was then output as a histogram (see Figure 2). Next the distributions of each sample were added, effectively producing the distribution for a ‘large’ sample measuring 900x900mm and the 300x300mm specimens were also subdivided to create smaller specimens. Normal distribution curves were fitted to the histograms using the data from the different specimen sizes (see Figure 3). In so doing, the statistical variability was characterized as a function of length scale. For clarity, only statistics representing the 900x900 and 300x300mm sample sizes are shown in Figure 3.

4 Modeling Tow Directional Variability

A computer code; ‘VariFab’, has been written to predict statistically representative variability in tow orientation across a textile sheet. VariFab is a kinematic algorithm that uses the same geometry-

Fig. 2. Image of typical distribution of angles from 1 of the 300x300mm specimens

Fig.3. Red lines are shear angle distributions calculated by summing each of the smaller distributions indicated by the blue lines for (a) srPP ‘off-the-roll’, (b) Twintex ‘off-the-roll’, (c) Woven glass fabric ‘off-the-roll’ and (d) Woven glass fabric exposed to handling

based mathematics as other pin-jointed net based kinematic codes [11 & 12]. In order to avoid the spurious tensile stresses that can occur if the tow reinforcement directions are randomly assigned and hence potentially discontinuous, each of the elements of the mesh is generated to be of rhombus geometry. Subsequent forming simulations will be performed such that the two directions of material anisotropy are aligned along the sides of the elements in the mesh. The simplest way to achieve this is to use truss elements to represent the reinforcement and membrane elements to provide shear resistance, e.g. [13-15]. Thus, the consistency of the tow directions within the forming simulations is assured.

Fig. 4. (a) Mesh with horizontal stretching of elements along the centerline. In this instance there is no vertical perturbation of nodes along the horizontal centerline (b) Mesh with both horizontal stretching of elements along the centerline and a vertical perturbation of the nodes along the horizontal centerline

Varifab produces this variability by two methods (see Figure 4): (a) by introducing horizontal stretching/contraction of elements along the horizontal centreline of the mesh and (b) by introducing additional perturbations of the nodes along the length of the horizontal and vertical centerlines. Both types of perturbation are transmitted to the rest of the mesh via pin-jointed net kinematics. The degree of variability can be controlled by changing the amount of stretching and the amplitude and wavelength of the perturbation. The mesh is generated from the origin and grows outwards. From this large mesh a selected region can be cut of arbitrary position and perimeter shape (see Figure 5). This latter feature permits further control of the variability within the mesh.

Fig 5. Selected regions that can be cut out of the larger mesh

4.1 Implementation of stretching of mesh

The side length of the elements, Λ , and position of the perimeter of the mesh are input by the user. The

degree of stretching/contraction along the horizontal centerline is also controlled by the user by specifying the diagonal length, μ_Δ , of elements at the centre of the mesh (see Figure 6a). Note that $\Lambda \leq \mu_\Delta \leq 2\Lambda$. Coordinates of nodes are determined using Eqs (1) & (2):

$$X = \begin{bmatrix} \left(-2 \sum_{i=1}^n a_n(i) \right) \\ \left(-2 \sum_{i=1}^n a_n(i) + a_n(n) \right) \\ \left(\left(-2 \sum_{i=1}^n a_n(i) + a_n(n) \right) + a_n(n-1) \right) \\ \cdot \\ \text{row}(n) + a_n(1) = S_a \\ S_a + a_n(1) \\ (S_a + a_n(1)) + a_n(2) \\ \cdot \\ (\text{row}(2n) + a_n(n)) \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

$$Y = \begin{bmatrix} (0) \\ (0 + b_n(n)) \\ ((0 + b_n(n)) + b_n(n-1)) \\ \cdot \\ \text{row}(n) + b_n(1) = S_b \\ S_b + b_n(1) \\ (S_b + b_n(1)) + b_n(2) \\ \cdot \\ (\text{row}(2n) + b_n(n)) \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

where X and Y are arrays that contain the coordinates of the outermost edge of the left quadrant of an expanding mesh (see Figure 4), n is the number of elements from the centre of the blank to either the right, left, top or bottom edge of the mesh (e.g. in Figure 4, $n=4$), i is the node number when counting outwards from the centre of the blank towards the outer edge of the mesh along the vertical or horizontal mesh centerlines (e.g. $n = 3$ for those nodes marked in red in Figure 4a). a_n is an array containing the half lengths of the horizontal diagonal element lengths (see Figure 6b).

$$2a_n = \left\{ \left(\mu_\Delta - \frac{4\Lambda}{\pi} \right) \varepsilon_n + \frac{4\Lambda}{\pi} \right\} \quad (3)$$

b_n is an array containing the half lengths of the vertical diagonal element lengths (see Figure 6b):

$$2b_n = \sqrt{\frac{\Lambda^2 - a_n^2}{4}} \quad (4)$$

ε_i is an array defined by Eq (5) which gradually decreases the stretch/contraction of the elements towards 0 when moving from the centre towards the left corner of the mesh

$$\varepsilon_n = \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{[0:1:n-1]}{n-1} \right)^2} \quad (5)$$

where $n \geq 3$. So far in this description, the horizontal and vertical diagonals of the cells (the blue lines in Figure 4) remain straight, leading to a limited degree of variability in the resulting mesh.

4.2 Implementation of perturbation of mesh

To increase the degree of variability, a perturbation can be added to Eqs (1) & (2). The wavelength and vertical amplitude of the perturbation is controlled using a sinusoidal function:

$$\delta_j(t) = A \sin(\omega_j t) \quad (6)$$

where A is the peak amplitude of the perturbation and $\omega_j t$ controls the periodicity of the perturbation.

The value of t has been chosen to lie between 0 and 5 and ω_j is an array;

$$\omega_j = [0 : (\pi/(j-1)) : \pi] \quad (7)$$

of size equal to the number of all nodes within the blank (number of nodes = j). The perturbed (x, y) coordinates of each node can be determined using Eqs. (8 & 9).

$$X_{pert} = X_j + A \sin(\omega_j t) \quad (8)$$

$$Y_{pert} = Y_j + A \sin(\omega_j t) \quad (9)$$

$$0 \leq A \leq \left(\frac{X_{max} - X_{min}}{10} \right) \quad 1 \leq \omega t \leq 5\pi$$

Fig.6. Varifab's geometrical parameters of (a) sketch of stretched sheet of fabric, (b) regular and irregular fabric unit cell

where X_j and Y_j are coordinates of nodes across the entire mesh, which are determined by the mapping technique once the upper left corner has been generated as described in Section 4.1.

5 Reproducing the Statistical Data

An important goal of this work is to ensure that variability generated by the VariFab code accurately reflects the actual variability measured from real textiles (see Figure 3). To this end, 'VarifabGA' has been designed using a genetic algorithm to automatically reproduce the same statistical distribution of shear angles observed in actual engineering fabrics and textile composites. Parameter space explored by VariFabGA includes: the stretched/contracted horizontal diagonal length, coordinates for the origin of the mesh and the amplitude and period of the perturbation. According to conventional genetic code nomenclature, any given set of input parameters is named an 'individual', 'chromosome' or 'state' [16-17]. The chromosomes in VariFabGA are thus comprised of a single row array including the parameters mentioned above. Each individual in a chromosome is named a 'gene' and is generated at random to lie within a predetermined range. Determination of the best individual chromosome from an arbitrary number of first generation chromosomes (typically 50) is based on a selection criteria that uses so-called 'fitness' or 'objective' functions [17-19]. Two fitness functions have been used in VarifabGA; Eqs (10 & 11), which are used to reproduce a blank with same normal distribution as the measured data.

$$FT_{mu} = \left| \frac{mu_m - mu_p}{mu_m} \right| \quad (10)$$

where FT_{mu} is the fitness function of the mean of the angle across the sheet, mu_m is the measured mean across a given specimen and mu_p is the predicted mean for a mesh of the same area.

$$FT_{std} = \left| \frac{std_m - std_p}{std_m} \right| \quad (11)$$

where FT_{std} is the fitness function of the standard deviation of the angle across the sheet, std_m is the standard deviation of the orientation angles and std_p is the predicted standard deviation [21]. The best

individual is selected by summing the two fitness functions (Eqs. 10 & 11) and choosing the individual with the smallest value. The reproduction technique used by VariFabGA is known as the Mutation technique [19-20]. The genes of the best chromosome selected from the first population are subsequently modified by adding a small random perturbation to every gene within the chromosome. The fitness function of the mutated gene is then determined; if the fitness is improved (closer to the target) this chromosome is retained for further mutation, if not then it is discarded and the previous chromosome is used for further mutation. The process continues until the chromosome's fitness is determined to be sufficiently close to the target to be considered satisfactorily converged. The time of convergence is based on the number of stopping criteria and the complexity of the problem. In this work, two fitness limit criteria have been considered, Eqs. (12 & 13).

$$FC_{mu} = |mu_m - mu_p| \quad (12)$$

$$FC_{std} = |std_m - std_p| \quad (13)$$

where FC_{mu} is the criteria of the mean and FC_{std} is the criteria of the standard deviation.

6 Digital Mesh Generation

As an example, Figure 7a shows a mesh predicted using statistics measured from a specific sample. Figure 7b shows these statistics (circular points) along with the statistics of the predicted mesh (blue line). Good agreement between the measured and predicted variability is achieved.

Fig.7. (a) Image of varifab mesh with same distribution as that in Figure 1b, (b) Use same distribution as in Figure 2 but now with the fitted distribution in another color.

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